

Proposal to Increase the Efficiency, Reliability and Safety of the Centre of Data Collection Management and Their Evaluation Using Cluster Solutions

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Abstract : This article deals with the possibility of increasing efficiency, reliability and safety of the system for teledosimetric data collection management and their evaluation as a part of complex study for activity "Research of data collection, their measurement and evaluation with mobile and autonomous units" within project "Research of monitoring and evaluation of non-standard conditions in the area of nuclear power plants". Possible weaknesses in existing system are identified. A study of available cluster solutions with possibility of their deploying to analysed system is presented.

Keywords : teledosimetric data, efficiency, reliability, safety, cluster solution

Conference Title : ICCSET 2014 : International Conference on Computer Science, Engineering and Technology

Conference Location : Toronto, Canada

Conference Dates : June 16-17, 2014